

EFFECTS OF ENVIRONMENT AND CURING ON THE STRENGTH OF ADHESIVE JOINTS

W.P. DE WILDE, G. VAN VINCKENROY, L. TIRRY, A.H. CARDON

Composite Systems and Adhesion Research Group of the University Brussels (COSARGUB)

Faculty of Applied Sciences - Free University Brussels (VUB)

Pleinlaan, 2

B-1050 Brussels, Belgium

ABSTRACT

The influence of four parameters - pretreatment of the adherend, curing cycle, time before testing and humidity - on the strength of adhesively bonded single lap joints is investigated for aluminium 2024-T3 adherend and modified epoxy FM73M adhesive. The importance of conditioning the aluminium surface prior to bonding is confirmed. The fitting of the experiments to a statistical distribution is examined to allow use of the experimental results for finite element techniques with probabilistic models.

INTRODUCTION

Finite element techniques are increasingly used to study the behaviour of an adhesively bonded single lap joint [1]. However, making a reliable prediction of the strength of a joint starting from the known properties of the adherend and the adhesive is not easy. This is particularly due to the difficulties that arise in modelling the interphase between the metal and the adhesive and its influence on the complete structure. The interphase properties and the resulting strength of the joint depend on the adherend surface treatment prior to bonding.

We have considered two kinds of parameters that influence the ultimate strength of a joint: fabrication parameters and post-fabrication parameters. Fabrication parameters such as the pretreatment of the adherend and the curing cycle are parameters that can be controlled or chosen in order to improve the final mechanical properties of the joint. After the fabrication, the strength of a joint can change with ageing or due to environmental exposure. These parameters, that are less often controllable, are called post-fabrication parameters.

The influences of all these parameters were investigated by comparison with a reference condition or by comparison of two extremely different test conditions.

To allow the use of probabilistic models instead of deterministic ones in structures simulations by means of the stochastic finite element method (SFEM), it has been investigated whether the experiments fit a statistical model. The complete procedure followed is described in [2]. It is based on a combination of various parameters estimation techniques and goodness-of-fit tests to determine the best fit distribution describing the phenomenon under investigation.

PREPARATION OF JOINTS

Plates of aluminium 2024-T3 with a thickness of 1.6 mm were cut according to the ASTM D-1002 standard (25.4 x 101.6 mm). The aluminium specimens were prepared as follows: first plates were cleaned with acetone and then they were roughened electrochemically (DC) for 90s at a current density $J=15 \text{ A/dm}^2$ in a solution of 0.1 M HCl at a temperature of 35°C. After this roughening process, the specimens were rinsed with distilled water and dried. Afterwards the specimens were immersed in a solution of 3% H_3PO_4 and 2% H_2CrO_3 at a temperature of 90°C for 180s to clean the surface. Finally the specimens were again rinsed with distilled water and dried. This surface treatment will be further on referred to as treatment #1. Once the adherends were prepared, they were bonded together with the FM73M adhesive which has a glass transition temperature of 120°C and is manufactured by the American Cyanamid Company. The joints were kept under vacuum for approximately 12 hours to avoid air inclusion. Subsequently, the adhesive was cured according to the manufacturer's recommended cure-cycle: heat up in 30 minutes to 120°C, hold 70 minutes at 120°C, with a pressure of 0.28 MPa, and cool down in 80 minutes to 25°C (1.2°C/min) before removing the pressure. This curing cycle will be further on referred to as curing cycle #1.

EXPERIMENTS ON JOINT FABRICATION PARAMETERS

INFLUENCE OF THE SURFACE CONDITIONING.

The importance of conditioning the aluminium surface prior to bonding has often been mentioned in the literature [3-6]. In order to examine the influence of the pretreatment described in previous section, a second pretreatment was used as a reference which consisted of cleaning the aluminium specimens with acetone, rinsing with distilled water and drying. This surface treatment will be further on referred to as treatment #2. After being cured (cure cycle #1), all joints were stored in a desiccator at room temperature for 10 days before their ultimate strength was determined by a tensile test. The tensile test was performed on an Instron machine coupled to a data acquisition system that recorded the tensile stress-strain curve. For each pretreatment, 15 joints were tested. The average and the dispersion of the experimentally determined strength values for both surface treatments are given in Table 1.

The joints prepared without any pretreatment appeared to be approximately 25% stronger than those prepared with the "full" treatment. Various explanations have been proposed. On one side, the native oxides present on aluminium could provide a better bonding surface than the specimens subjected to the full pretreatment. Another explanation for this unexpected result could be found in the first step in the pretreatment, namely the roughening in 0.1M HCl. Bishopp had already warned against the negative effects of roughening the aluminium surface prior to bonding [7]. Using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis, Bishopp noticed air blisters in the glueline and concluded that because of the high degree of roughness, not all the air trapped between the adhesive and the adherend could be displaced during the cure cycle which reduced the contact surface area between the adhesive and the adherend. However, in the fabrication procedure followed here, the air has been removed before curing by applying vacuum. As a consequence, no air inclusions were found in the glueline. Analysis with SEM showed that roughening the aluminium surface resulted in high local discontinuities. The non-treated specimens, on the contrary, showed a fairly homogeneous surface. It is assumed that due to these high discontinuities at the aluminium surface, high stress concentrations arise locally that can initiate the fracture.

It has been investigated whether a statistical model could be fitted to the results of the tensile tests. Four statistical distributions were tried: the normal, the log-normal, the Weibull, the smallest (SEV) and the largest (LEV) extreme-value distributions. For each distribution, the corresponding parameters were determined together with the goodness-of-fit measure, which gives an indication of how good the respective distribution fits the experiments: greater the value, better the fit. The data from the joints manufactured using the full pretreatment

(treatment #1) could be fitted by two distributions, i.e. the Weibull and the smallest extreme value distributions, with at least a 98% level confidence (Table 1). For the joints submitted to treatment #2, the largest extreme value distribution is the best fit distribution, with a 99% level confidence.

Table 1: Influence of the surface conditioning on joint strength

	strength of etched joints (MPa) (treatment #1)	strength of acetone cleaned joints (MPa) (treatment #2)
average	24.62	31.24
standard deviation	1.77	1.91
Normal distribution	corr.= 0.92	corr.= 0.90
μ	24.62	31.24
σ	1.77	1.91
Log-normal distribution	corr.= 0.85	corr.= 0.93
μ	3.201	3.44
σ	0.070	0.058
2p-Weibull distribution	corr.= 0.98	corr.= 0.74
η	16.7	17.927
σ	25.4	32.137
SEVdistribution	corr.= 0.99	corr.= 0.57
η	1.76	1.792
μ	25.47	32.205
LEV distribution	corr.= 0.62	corr.= 0.99
η	1.6	1.50
μ	23.8	30.39

INFLUENCE OF COOLING

Once the joints were fully cured, changes in the curing cycle (longer curing time, higher temperature) had little influence on the ultimate strength of the joints. Nevertheless, the ultimate strength appeared to be especially sensitive to the cooling down procedure after the curing process. As a reference, a very slow cooling rate was applied to specimens that received the full pretreatment. To do so, the oven was turned off after the hold procedure and the specimens are allowed to cool down slowly. Approximately 4 hours were necessary to cool the joints to 30°C, a rate of 0.4°C/min instead of 1.2°C/min. Seven joints were cooled down in this manner and the ultimate strength was determined after 3 days (for three joints) and 10 days (for four joints): no evolution of the strength with time was noticed. The ultimate strength of all the joints was approximately 37.20 MPa, with a standard deviation of 0.53 MPa. This strength is very high compared with the 24.62 MPa that is found with the normal cooling procedure.

EXPERIMENTS ON POST-FABRICATION PARAMETERS

INFLUENCE OF AGEING

The time that the joints were kept after curing, but before being submitted to a tensile test, influenced the joint strength. Therefore, 40 joints were prepared as described previously. After the curing process, the joints were kept dry in a desiccator until the specimens were tested. The strength of the joints was determined after 10 days for 15 joints, 20 days for 10 joints, and 30 days for 15 joints. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Influence of ageing on joint strength.

	strength of joints dry stored during 20 days (MPa)	strength of joints dry stored during 30 days (MPa)
average	34.32	34.60
standard deviation	2.12	1.62
Normal distribution	corr.= 0.86	corr.= 0.86
μ	34.32	34.60
σ	2.12	1.62
Log-normal distribution	corr.= 0.84	corr.= 0.80
μ	3.53	3.54
σ	0.061	0.046
2p-Weibull distribution	corr.= 0.98	corr.= 0.99
η	21.07	28.60
σ	35.25	35.30
SEV distribution	corr.= 0.98	corr.= 0.99
η	1.61	1.21
μ	35.30	35.33
LEV distribution	corr.= 0.80	corr.= 0.60
η	2.09	1.68
μ	33.25	33.77

During the first 30 days the joint strength increased gradually, but after 30 days it approached the strength of the joints that were cooled down very slowly after curing. Post-test analysis of the surface with SEM showed that with increasing time, the locus of failure evolves to a more cohesive crack in the adhesive. We assume that, due to adhesive shrinkage, stresses increased during the (forced) cooling and that with time a stress-relaxation occurs. Although the joint strength increases, no changes in statistical behaviour with time were found (Table 2).

INFLUENCE OF HUMIDITY

To investigate the influence of environmental exposure, joints were prepared as described previously and stored in a humidity chamber at a temperature of 70°C and a relative humidity of 75%. The 70°C temperature was chosen as a compromise between accelerating the effect of moisture absorption [8] and staying far below the glass transition temperature of the adhesive. The strength of joints submitted to the full surface conditioning (treatment #1) was determined after periods of 10, 20 and 30 days (Table 3).

Table 3: Influence of environment on joint strength.

strength of joints stored with T=70°C and R.H.=75% during 10 days (MPa)	strength of joints stored with T=70°C and R.H.=75% during 20 days (MPa)	strength of joints stored with T=70°C and R.H.=75% during 30 days (MPa)
25.95	25.16	24.15
1.40	1.31	1.78

It is well known that humidity decreases the strength of a joint due to adhesive swelling and also due to a modification of the structure of the aluminium oxide surface. When the oxide layer absorbs water, the following structural changes can occur [9]:

Aluminium hydroxide, however, does not adhere well to the base metal or to the adhesive. The weight-increase of aluminium specimens was measured periodically for 30 days while they were stored in a humidity chamber at a temperature of 70°C and a relative humidity of 75%. After 30 days saturation was achieved and a weight-increase of 2.10⁻³% was found.

The importance of forming stable oxide layers in obtaining good joint strength has been reported in literature [10]. The following experiment confirmed this. Seven joints were prepared as described in section 3 (these were only cleaned with acetone) and kept 10 days in a humidity chamber at a temperature of 70°C and a relative humidity of 75%. The strength of these joints decreased drastically to 24.5 MPa. Joints that had received the full pretreatment (treatment #1) gave better results in a wet environment, probably because of the use of H₃PO₄ during the surface treatment. Phosphate ions are known to form stable oxide layers and to inhibit hydration reaction in a wet environment.

No statistical treatment has been performed due to the too small amount of data available.

CONCLUSIONS

Great importance should be given to the different steps of the pretreatment of the adherend. Also, the pretreatment should be appropriate for the environmental conditions under which the joint will be used. For instance, joints that are exposed to high humidity retain reasonable strength if they are conditioned adequately.

Caution should be exercised in roughening aluminium surfaces prior to bonding. It is a general belief that roughening the adherend surface increases the contact surface area between the adhesive and the adherend and therefore the joint strength. The roughening method used in the present study resulted in a poorer joint strength. The authors believe that this is due to stress-concentrations that arise at the adherends surface. The influence of different roughening methods has not been investigated.

The cooling rate of the joints after the curing process appears to be important. A slow cooling rate (0.4°C/min) provided the best results in this study. Cooling of joints at a rate of 1.2°C/min provided satisfactory strengths if the joints were kept in dry conditions approximately 30 days before loading.

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